

ADSORPTION OF ACIDS, BASES AND ALKALOIDS BY SYNTHETIC ION-EXCHANGE RESINS

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The adsorption of acids and alkalis on synthetic resins follows the Freundlich adsorption isotherm. The results indicate surface adsorption rather than chemical interaction between the functional groups on the surface of the resins and the acid or alkali in solution.

The order of the total acidities of the cationic resins, as determined by potentiometric titrations with alkali, may not agree with that of the adsorptive powers as found from the adsorption isotherms. The study of both adsorption isotherms and titration curves would afford a more complete picture of the adsorption characteristics.

The anionic resins appear to exhibit true anion-exchange rather than molecular adsorption of acids.

The order of adsorption of alkaloids, in a number of cationic resins, does not agree with that for alkali as obtained from titration curves, and further, this order varies with different alkaloids.

Adams and Holmes (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1935, 54, 11) first drew attention to the adsorbing powers of resins from polyhydric phenols and formaldehyde for various cations. Bhatnagar and co-workers (*this Journal*, 1936, 13, 679 ; 1939, 16, 249, 262, 361) concluded that adsorption from solutions by these resins followed the ordinary laws of adsorption and hence must be considered a surface phenomenon.

Myers ("Advances in Colloid Science", Vol. I, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1942, p. 333) considered that the exchange phenomena on synthetic resins should be regarded as metathetical chemical reactions between the electrolytes in solution and the active groups on the surface. This primary process is, however, so masked by diffusion and reaction velocity factors, that the practical equilibrium values simulate adsorption phenomena.

Equations of exchange equilibria for cation-exchange resins were formulated by Griessbach ("Über die Herstellung und Anwendung neuerer Austausch adsorbierenten, insbesondere auf Hartzbasis", Verlag Chemie, Berlin, 1939) on the basis of the Freundlich adsorption isotherm and by Boyd, Schubert and Adamson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 67, 2818) on the basis of the Langmuir isotherm as well as of the law of mass action. There now appears to be a general agreement regarding the fundamental nature of cation-exchange on synthetic resins. But since the observed characteristics vary from one resin to another, depending upon the nature of the acidic groups and the texture (which determines available surface and accessibility of the active groups), the necessity is felt for further data on the characteristics of various types of synthetic resins with a view to judging their suitability for application in different fields.

With anion-exchange resins, however, the nature of the interactions is not so clear. Until recently, the view was prevalent that these amine type resins adsorb acids molecularly instead of exchanging anions (Schwartz, Edwards and Boudreaux, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1940, 32, 1462 ; Griessbach, *loc. cit.*) On the other hand, the work of Jenny

(*J. Colloid Sci.*, 1946, 1, 33), Sussman (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1945, 37, 618) and of Kunin and Myers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2874) indicate that these are true anion exchangers. Further evidence seems to be necessary for the clarification of the mechanism of adsorption by anion-exchange resins.

Most of the industrial applications on ion-exchange resins, till now, have been in the field of water de-ionisation, and the methods of characterisation and evaluation of the resins, developed so far, are mostly concerned with the requirements of water-treatment operations. There is, however, promise of the large-scale employment of synthetic ion-exchange resins for other purposes as well, e.g., for the isolation of alkaloids (cf. Applezweig and Ronzone, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1946, 38, 576; Mukherjee, *J. Proc. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 1947, 19, 61). Preliminary observations on the adsorption and elution of quinine on ion-exchange columns have been made in this laboratory (Mukherjee and Sen Gupta, *ibid.*, 1949, 21, 83), but irregularities have often been noticed, which have been ascribed to the kinetics of the ion-exchange process.

In the present work, studies have been made on the fundamental adsorptive properties of a number of synthetic cation- and anion-exchange resins, available in the market, as also on the adsorption of alkaloids by cationic resins, both under static and dynamic (column) conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthetic Resins.—Three cationic resins—Zeokarb*, amberlite IR-100** and Ionac C-284†, and two anionic resins—Deacidite* and Ionac A-293† were used for the experiments.

Preparation of Standard Forms of Resins.—For preparing the *hydrogen form* the *cationic resin* was kept in contact with standard sulphuric acid, with frequent shaking. After 24 hours, the acid was decanted off and its strength determined and fresh standard acid added to the resin. This was repeated until the acid suffered no loss of strength after 24 hours' contact with the resin. The actual period of contact required was in most cases 72 hours. The resin was washed with water and kept under water with intermittent shaking. After 24 hours the water was filtered off and estimated for acid content and the resin suspended in fresh water. This was continued until the wash water did not show titratable acidity after 24 hours' contact. The resin was dried to a constant weight at 40°.

For determining the residual acid in the resin, 1 g. of the latter was kept in contact with 50 c.c. of water for one week with intermittent shaking. The acidity of the water was estimated at the end of this period.

The *alkali forms* of the *anionic resins* were prepared in a similar manner, replacing the standard acid with standard caustic soda solution.

"Acid forms" of the anionic resins and "alkali forms" of the cationic resins were prepared in the following manner. The resin was kept in contact with 0.1N sulphuric acid or caustic soda solution, with periodical replacement, till "saturation" was reached.

*From the Permutit Company, U. S. A.

**From the American Cyanamid Company, U. S. A.

†From the Resinous Products & Chemical Company, U. S. A.

It was filtered and washed on the filter with alcohol in order to remove free acid or alkali adhering to the resin and dried to a constant weight at 40°.

Adsorption Measurements.—The resin (1 g.) was suspended in 50 c. c. of the appropriate solution of the electrolyte, kept for 24 hours with intermittent shaking, and the solution was then analysed.

Potentiometric Titrations.—The acid forms of the cationic resins were titrated potentiometrically with caustic soda and the alkali forms of the anionic resins similarly titrated with sulphuric acid. The standard forms, prepared using 1*N* solutions of acid or alkali, were used for this purpose. Varying amounts of 0.1*N* sulphuric acid or caustic soda were taken in a series of reagent bottles, water was added to bring the volume to 10 c.c. in every case, and 0.2 g. of the resin was added to each bottle. The mixture was shaken intermittently and allowed to stand for 24 hours after which the p_H of the supernatant liquid was determined with a p_H meter. (It was found by a preliminary experiment that increasing the period beyond 24 hours did not produce any further change of p_H). The results have been plotted graphically in Figs. 1 and 2.

FIG 1

Potentiometric titration curves of acid forms of cationic resins with NaOH.

The curve indicated by rectangle refers to H-Zeocrab-215, that by triangle, H-Ionac-C-284 and the one by circle, H-Amberlite IR-100.

Standard Forms of Synthetic Resins

For purposes of characterisation and comparison of exchange capacities of different resins, these should be reduced to standard conditions (*i. e.* to hydrogen or hydroxyl forms). But reference to the literature does not show any uniformity of procedure in this respect. Various concentrations of acid or alkali have been recommended for

this purpose, e.g., 1 or 2% (Myers, Eastes and Myers, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1941, 33, 637), 2% (Myers and Eastes, *ibid.*, 1941, 33, 1203), 1 N (Kunin and Myers, *loc. cit.*) and 5N (Boyd, Schubert and Adamson, *loc. cit.*).

FIG. 2

Potentiometric titration curves of alkali forms of anionic resins with H₂SO₄.

The upper curve refers to Na-Deacidite and the lower one to Na-Ionac A-293.

In view of the above, a study was made of the effect of concentration of acid or alkali on the properties of the resultant acid or alkali forms of the resins. The acid forms of the cationic resins were prepared with 0.1N and 1.0N sulphuric acid and those of the anionic resins were prepared using 1.0N caustic soda. For one cationic resin, Amberlite IR-100, the acid forms were prepared using 3N acid also.

The alkali or acid consumptions from 0.1N solutions by the acidic or alkaline resins, respectively, were determined and the results are given in Table I. The adsorption has in all cases been expressed in terms of normal acid or alkali consumed per g. of the resin.

TABLE I

Synthetic resins.	1.0N-H ₂ SO ₄ or NaOH consumed by 1 g. of resin treated with H ₂ SO ₄ or NaOH		
	0.1N.	1.0N.	3.0N.
Amberlite IR-100 (H ₂ SO ₄ -treated)	2.86 c.c.	2.75	2.88
Zeokarb 215 (H ₂ SO ₄ -treated)	3.70	2.93	—
Ionac C-284 (H ₂ SO ₄ -treated)	3.52	3.50	—
Ionac A-293 (NaOH-treated)	4.10	4.18	—
Deacidite (NaOH-treated)	5.00	5.00	—

The above results show that the standard forms are independent of the concentration of the acid or alkali used for their preparation. The discrepancy observed with Zeokarb should probably be attributed to incomplete washing of the acid resin prepared with 0.1N acid. For this resin, the latter form was not used in any subsequent studies.

The presence of free and diffusible acid or alkali in the standard forms of resins was investigated by keeping the resins in contact with water for seven days (Table XI). The results show that acid forms of cationic resins or the alkali forms of anionic resins contain negligible amount of free acid or alkali, but the opposite numbers contain an appreciable amount of free acid or alkali. This has been referred to later again.

The "Suspension effect" in Synthetic Resins

Wiegner and Pallman (Sub Kommission der Internationalen. Boden. Gessel., 1929, p. 92) observed that in certain aqueous suspensions the supernatant liquid had a different p_H from that of the suspension. Mukherjee, Mitra and Mukherjee (*Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci.*, 1937, 1, 227) observed the same phenomenon in colloidal suspensions of acidic substances, viz., silicic acid, palmitic acid and hydrogen clays, and attributed this to the osmotic activity of the mobile hydrogen ions in the liquid side of the electrical double layer on the surface of the particles. The acid forms of the cationic resins should also come under this category, and so determinations were made of the p_H of the supernatant liquid and of the moist resin residue after removing most of the free water by decantation, using a glass electrode. For the latter determinations, care was taken to pile up the resin magma around the electrode to ensure efficient contact with the electrode surface and to maintain electrolytic contact. Equilibrium was attained slowly and the final readings were taken when constant values of p_H were obtained. The determinations were made on suspensions at an advanced stage of washing, and the supernatant liquids were in contact with the resins for 48 hours, with frequent shaking, before the measurements were taken in order to ensure the establishment of equilibrium. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Suspension effect in synthetic resins.

Synthetic resins and treatment with acid.	Supernatant liquid.	p_H of	Resin magma.
Amberlite IR-100 treated with 0.1N-H ₂ SO ₄	4.86		2.00
" " 1.0 "	3.48*		2.04
" " 3.0 "	4.38		2.00
Zeokarb " 1.0 "	4.56		2.24
Ionac C284 " 1.0 "	4.00		2.08

*A large ratio of resin : water was used in this case.

The results show a significant difference between the p_H of the supernatant liquid and the resin magma, and point to the existence of a suspension effect in these cases also.

Adsorption of Acids, Alkali and Neutral Salts by Standard Forms of Resins

The acid and alkali forms of resins, used for these experiments, were prepared using 0.1N sulphuric acid or caustic soda, excepting Zeokarb, for which 1.0N concentration of acid was used. The results are shown in Table III to XI.

TABLE III

Adsorption of caustic soda by acid forms of cationic resins.

Initial conc. of NaOH.	Zeokarb 215		H-Amberlite IR-100		H-Ionac C-184	
	Equilib. conc. of NaOH.	Adsorption of NaOH. (c.c. of N-NaOH)	Equilib. conc. of NaOH.	Adsorption of NaOH. (c.c. of N-NaOH).	Equilib. conc. of NaOH.	Adsorption of NaOH. (c.c. of N-NaOH).
1.00N	0.8999N	5.0	0.9080N	4.60	0.9020N	4.90
0.50	0.4040	4.8	0.4120	4.40	0.4104	4.84
0.333	0.2440	4.46	0.2512	4.10	—	—
0.25	—	—	—	—	0.1660	4.20
0.20	0.1194	4.03	0.1296	3.52	0.1190	4.05
0.167	—	—	—	—	0.0860	4.03
0.143	0.0709	3.59	0.0783	3.22	—	—
0.125	0.0549	3.50	0.0629	3.10	0.0479	3.83
0.100	0.0374	3.13	0.0428	2.86	0.0296	3.52
0.667	0.0167	2.48	0.0204	2.31	0.0070	2.98

TABLE IV

Adsorption of sulphuric acid by acid form of Zeokarb.

Initial conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ .	Equilib. conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ .	Adsorption of H ₂ SO ₄ (c.c. of N-H ₂ SO ₄).
1.06N	1.051N	0.16
0.53	0.517	0.12
0.21	0.203	0.176
0.08	0.074	0.12
0.06	0.054	0.12
0.04	0.036	0.08

TABLE V

Adsorption of sulphuric acid by alkali forms of anionic resins.

Initial conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ .	Na-Deacidite		Na-Ionac A-293	
	Equilib. conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ .	Adsorption of H ₂ SO ₄ (c.c. of N-H ₂ SO ₄).	Equilib. conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ .	Adsorption of H ₂ SO ₄ (c.c. of N-H ₂ SO ₄).
0.50N	0.3159N	3.53	0.376N	5.65
0.20	0.0349	0.25	0.045	3.02
0.143	0.0036	0.45	0.040	4.44
0.100	0.0000	3.00	0.0180	4.10

TABLE VI

Adsorption of hydrochloric acid by alkali forms of anionic resins.

Initial conc. of HCl.	Na-Deacidite		Na-Ionac A-293	
	Equilib. conc. of HCl.	Adsorption of HCl (c.c. of N-HCl).	Equilib. conc. of HCl.	Adsorption of HCl. (c.c. of N-HCl).
0.50 N	0.3420N	7.90	0.4151N	4.25
0.20	0.0634	6.82	0.1201	4.00
0.143	0.0178	6.25	0.0700	3.64
0.100	0.0150	4.25	0.0320	3.40

TABLE VII

Adsorption of sulphuric acid by alkali forms of cationic resins.

Initial conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ .	Na-Zeokarb		Na-Amberlite IR-100		Na-Ionac C-284	
	Equilib. conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ .	Adsorption of H ₂ SO ₄ . (c.c. of N-H ₂ SO ₄)	Equilib. conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ .	Adsorption of H ₂ SO ₄ . (c.c. of N-H ₂ SO ₄).	Equilib. conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ .	Adsorption of H ₂ SO ₄ . (c.c. of N-H ₂ SO ₄).
1.00N	0.9038N	4.80	0.9428N	2.86	0.9301N	3.40
0.50	0.4209	3.95	0.4468	2.66	0.4370	3.75
0.333	0.2590	3.71	0.2811	2.60	—	—
0.25	—	—	—	—	0.1930	2.85
0.20	0.1380	3.10	0.1508	2.46	0.1570	2.75
0.167	...	—	—	—	0.1120	2.73
0.143	0.0839	2.94	0.0946	2.40	—	—
0.125	0.0680	2.85	0.0783	2.32	0.0739	2.55
0.100	0.0439	2.80	0.0563	2.18	0.0520	2.40
0.0667	0.0152	2.57	0.0264	2.01	0.0216	2.25

TABLE VIII

Adsorption of caustic soda by acid forms of anionic resins.

Initial conc. of NaOH.	H-Deacidite		H-Ionac A-293	
	Equilib. conc. of NaOH.	Adsorption of NaOH. (c.c. of N-NaOH).	Equilib. conc. of NaOH.	Adsorption of NaOH (c.c. of N-NaOH).
0.50N	0.3819N	5.90	0.4185N	4.07
0.25	0.1395	5.52	0.1726	3.87
0.167	0.0600	5.30	0.0920	3.73
0.125	0.0180	5.35	0.0540	3.55
0.100	0.0043	4.78	0.0335	3.32

TABLE IX

Interaction of salts with acid forms of cationic resins.

Conc. of salt		Acid liberated in solution in terms of c.c. of N HCl.		
KCl.	BaCl ₂ .	H-Zeokarb.	H-Amberlite IR-100.	H-Ionac C-284
0.1N	—	1.325	0.825	—
0.2	—	1.50	0.85	1.575
1.0	—	1.625	0.925	—
—	0.1N	1.625	0.95	—
—	0.2	1.65	1.025	1.725
—	1.0	1.675	1.025	—

TABLE X

Interaction of salts with alkali forms of anionic resins.

Salt used.	Conc. of salt.	Alkali liberated in solution (c.c. of N-KOH).	
		Na-Deacidite.	Na-Ionac A-293.
KCl	0.2N	0.5	0.15
K ₂ SO ₄	0.2	0.8	0.10
K ₂ HPO ₄	0.2	0.8	0.40

TABLE XI

Free acid or alkali in standard forms of resins.

(After 7 days' contact with water)

Resin used.	Standard form.	Liberation of free acid or alkali	
		N-H ₂ SO ₄ .	N-NaOH.
Zeokarb	Acid	0.02 c.c.	—
"	Alkali	—	0.63 c.c.
Amberlite IR-100	Acid	0.025	—
"	Alkali*	—	0.46
Ionac C-284	Acid	0.048	—
"	Alkali	—	0.08
Deacidite	Acid	0.25	—
"	Alkali	—	0.05
Ionac A-293	Acid	0.62	—
"	Alkali	—	0.02

Adsorption of Alkali.—Figures 3 and 4 contain curves obtained by plotting the logarithms of the amounts adsorbed against the logarithms of the equilibrium concentrations of the adsorbate in solution. It will be found that the curves are generally linear, which indicates that the Freundlich adsorption isotherm is obeyed in all these cases.

FIG. 3
Adsorption Isotherms.

The curves in order from top to bottom refer respectively to H_2SO_4 on Na-Deacidite ; NaOH on H-Zeokrab 215 ; NaOH on H-Ionac-C-284 ; NaOH on H-Amberlite IR-100 ; and H_2SO_4 on Na-Ionac A-293.

For the adsorption of alkali by acid forms of resins, the isotherms for Amberlite IR-100 and Zeokarb run nearly parallel, but that for Ionac C-28 has a lower slope.

If the interaction between the acid form of a cationic resin and an alkali in solution be regarded as chemical neutralisation of the surface acid groups, the amount of alkali neutralised by the resin would correspond stoichiometrically to the number of neutralisable acidic groups and would be independent of the concentration of the alkali employed, provided that its quantity was so chosen that an excess remained at the end. Myers (*loc. cit.*) attributed the resemblance of such phenomena to an adsorption process to the disturbing effects of diffusion and reaction velocity. But in the experiments described above, sufficient time was allowed for the resin to come to equilibrium with the alkali solution, and therefore those factors do not come into play. The interaction appears to be a true adsorption process (cf. Bhatnagar *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

The similarity in the slopes of the isotherms for Zeokarb and Amberlite points to a similarity in the adsorbing nature of the two surfaces, the difference in level indicating the difference in the number of active centres. But the two resins are quite different chemically, the former being a sulphonated coal and the latter, a resin of phenol-formaldehyde type, treated with sulphite. The resemblance lies in the surface properties rather than in the chemical nature of the adsorbing groups

The alkali adsorption curves for the acidic forms of anionic resins have a relatively small slope (Fig. 5). It would appear that here the hydrogen ions associated with the resins are more easily available for neutralisation, and consequently increase in the concentration of the alkali makes smaller difference. The isotherm would still indicate an adsorption process, possibly the adsorption of hydroxyl ions on the surface.

Adsorption of Acids—The isotherms for the adsorption of sulphuric acid on alkali forms of anionic resins (Fig. 4) are also typical of an adsorption process. The question is whether the acid is adsorbed molecularly, or it is an ion-exchange process. The results of the interaction of salts with the alkali forms of anionic resins throw light on this point (Table XI). Alkali is liberated as a result of this interaction and potassium sulphate or phosphate liberates more alkali than the chloride. This can be regarded as the exchange of surface hydroxyl ions for the anions of the added electrolyte, and one with a higher valency has a greater capacity for displacing the hydroxyl ions. This observation supports those of Jenny (*loc. cit.*) and of Kunin and Myers (*loc. cit.*).

FIG. 4

Curves from top to bottom refer respectively to

- (a) NaOH on H-Deacidite,
- (b) NaOH on H-Ionac A-293,
- (c) H₂SO₄ on Na-Zeokrab 215,
- (d) H₂SO₄ on Na-Ionac C-281,
- (e) H₂SO₄ on Amberlite IR 100 and
- (f) NaOH on H-Zeokrab 215

A comparison of Tables V and VI will show that sulphuric acid is adsorbed more strongly than hydrochloric acid. This is in accordance with the observation made above that sulphate ions have a greater displacing power than chloride ions.

The curves for the adsorption of acid by the alkali forms of cationic resins (Fig 2) are less steep than those for the anionic resins. Neutralisation of loosely bound alkali, coupled with adsorption of hydrogen ions, appears to be indicated.

The adsorption of sulphuric acid on the acidic form of Zeokarb presents a peculiar feature (Table IV, Fig 4.). A small but definite adsorption is noticed which, however, does not vary significantly with the concentration of acid employed.

Potentiometric Titration Curves

The titration curves for Zeokarb, Amberlite and Ionac (Fig. 1) show that all the three have a strong acid character, but the total acidities vary in the order: Ionac C-284 > Amberlite IR-100 > Zeokarb 215. The curve for Zeokarb shows a sharper inflexion than the other two, but beyond this point the curve flattens at a lower p_n , indicating a buffering effect between p_n 9 and 10. Resins having sulphonic acid as the functional group are known to adsorb at low p_n values, but the shape of the titration curve points to the existence of other types of groups also, which can adsorb hydrogen ions in the alkaline region. Similarly, Amberlite appears to have a stronger buffer action than Ionac at p_n below 11.

The titration curves for anionic resins (Fig. 2) show an entirely different character. The curve for Ionac A-293 shows continuous variation of p_n , with only a slight break between p_n 3 and 4, and hence resembles that of an extremely weak base. The titration curve for Deacidite resembles that of a moderately weak base, showing a short buffering range above p_n 5 and an inflexion between p_n 4 and 5. The total acidity of the latter is also somewhat greater than that of the former, both being calculated from the inflexion points.

Exchange Capacities of Resins

If the end-points of the titration curves indicate the complete neutralisation of the acidic or basic groups on the surface of the resins, these would also represent the total base or acid binding (or exchange) capacities of the materials. The values, so calculated, are given in Table XII. The results are expressed as milli-equivalents of acid or base bound per g. of the resin.

TABLE XII

Base or acid binding capacities obtained from titration curves.

Cationic resin.	Base binding capacity (m.e./g.).	Anionic resin.	Acid binding capacity (m.e./g.)
Zeokarb 215	0.833	Ionac A-293	5.0
Amberlite IR-100	1.250	Deacidite	5.83
Ionac C-284	2.083		

A reference to Table III will, however, show that the base-adsorption capacities of the three cationic resins vary in the order :

Ionac C-284 > Zeokarb 215 > Amberlite IR-100.

The discrepancy is difficult to explain except by attributing to the fact that while the base adsorption figures given in Table XII correspond to p_H values between 6 and 8 of the solutions, those in Table III correspond to the highly alkaline region. It has been observed above that Zeokarb, which has the lowest base binding capacity at the point of inflexion (p_H 6.5), shows base adsorption in the alkaline region, and this would explain the high value for base adsorption by Zeokarb in Table III. The titration curves for Amberlite and Ionac would similarly explain the greater base adsorption shown by the former from alkaline solutions.

It would thus appear that neither the adsorption isotherm nor the titration curve is alone sufficient to characterise the base binding properties of cationic resins. A study of both would give a more complete picture. For anionic resins, however, both appear to lead to similar results.

The Adsorption of Alkaloids

Since the isolation and separation of alkaloids promise to be a potential field of application of synthetic resins, a comparative study was made of the adsorptions of quinine, strychnine and caffeine, from solutions of their salts, on the acid forms of cation-exchange resins. The results are shown in Table XIII. The initial concentration of the alkaloid salt solution was, in each case, 0.02M.

TABLE XIII

Adsorption of alkaloids by cationic resins.

Alkaloid salt.	H-Zeokarb 215		H-Amberlite IR-100		H-Ionac C-284	
	Equilib. conc. of alkaloid.	Adsorption (mg./g.).	Equilib. conc. of alkaloid.	Adsorption (mg./g.).	Equilib. conc. of alkaloid.	Adsorption (mg./g.).
Quinine sulphate (in 0.02 N-H ₂ SO ₄)	0.0121M	127.5	0.0187M	19.8	0.0083M	311.4
Strychnine hydrochloride (neutral soln.)	0.0090	183.8	0.0168	53.5	0.0002	331.7
Do (in 0.02 N-HCl)	0.0095	173.9	0.0176	40.1	0.0002	330.3
Caffeine hydrochloride (neutral soln.)	0.0096	100.6	0.0096	106.2	0.0110	87.4
Do (in 0.02 N-HCl)	0.0100	96.8	0.0084	112.4	0.0115	82.8

The results in Table XIII show that a resin having a high adsorptive power for one alkaloid, may not behave similarly for a different alkaloid. In Table XIV, the relative adsorptive powers of the different resins for each of the alkaloids studied have been shown, the number 1, 2 and 3 representing a descending order of magnitude.

TABLE XIV

Relative orders of adsorption of alkaloids.

No.	Quinine.	Strychnine.	Caffeine.
1	H-Ionac C-284	H-Ionac C-284	H-Amberlite IR-100
2	H-Zeokarb 215	H-Zeokarb 215	H-Zeokarb 215
3	H-Amberlite IR-100	H-Amberlite IR-100	H-Ionac C-284

The relative order of adsorption for quinine and strychnine (Table XIV) agrees with the order of base-adsorption capacities as determined by adsorption isotherms, but not with that obtained from the potentiometric titration curves. Again, from the practical point of view, one must consider the kinetics of the adsorption and the effects of grain size. Thus, it was found that, for the adsorption of quinine in ion-exchange columns, Zeokarb adsorbed the alkaloid more readily than Ionac during the percolation, although the latter has a higher adsorbing power under static equilibrium conditions.

The above studies are intended to draw attention to the complexities in the phenomena of adsorption of synthetic resins and to the various factors which need study before a proper choice of a resin can be made and the conditions established for any practical application.

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